

The fertility expression of IR73827-23S in a field at Wuhan, China, in 2003.

Table 2. Yield trials of some two-line hybrids, China, 2003.

Location	Combination	Growth duration (d) ^a	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over check (%)
Hainan	IR73827-23S/Luhui 6	134	11.80	12.0
	IR73827-23S/TMQ30349	137	12.26	16.4
	IR73827-23S/R615	135	11.67	10.8
	Shanyou 63 (check)	141	10.53	
Wuhan	IR73827-23S/Mianhiu501	133	8.23	19.0
	IR73827-23S/Minghui63	130	7.50	8.5
	IR73827-23S/TMQ30349	130	8.33	20.6
	IR73827-23S/R524	130	8.80	27.4
	IR73827-23S/TMQ30506	132	9.33	35.1
	IR73827-23S/TMQ30525	128	7.73	11.9
	Il-You 725 (check)	129	6.91	

^a Days from seeding to maturity.

References

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Response of transgenic rice expressing two *Bt* genes to nontarget insects

K. Bashir, T. Husnain, and S. Riazuddin, National Centre of Excellence in Molecular Biology (CEMB), 87-W, Canal Bank Road, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

Different transgenic lines of indica basmati rice (Basmati 370) expressing *cry1Ac*, *cry2A*, or *cry1Ac* + *cry2A* genes were selected on the basis of molecular analysis and insect bioassays. During the first year (2001), 396 plants of five

different lines, along with the untransformed control, were sown following a randomized complete block design at CEMB, while a total of 3,000 plants of four transgenic lines expressing two *Bt* genes were randomized following a

split-plot design at CEMB and at Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, during the second year (2002). These lines showed a high level of resistance to yellow stem borer and rice leafhopper throughout the entire growth

season (Bashir et al, unpubl. data).

The specificity of *cry* genes for target insects is a great advantage in planning for field testing of transgenic lines containing such toxins. It is interesting to check the response of insects belonging to insect orders other than Lepidoptera and Diptera to transgenic lines expressing *Bt* genes at a high dose. A common method to check the response of transgenic lines to such insects is to compare the damage caused by these insects in transgenic lines and a control (Fitt et al 1994, Sims 1995, Orr and Landis 1998, Bashir et al 2004).

In our studies, 15 plants per plot per line were selected to study the extent of damage caused by nine different insects of three orders (Hemiptera, Homoptera, and Orthoptera) belonging to five different families. These insect species were first identified in the experimental field and the damage they caused was characterized. The number of leaves damaged by any of these

insects per plant was counted and expressed as a percentage of total leaves. Data were processed by analysis of variance, followed by Duncan's multiple range test. No statistical difference was observed between the damage in the transgenic lines and that in the control in any case. During the first year, the average damage in the transgenic lines was 7.84% as compared with 7.40% in the untransformed control. The following year, damage in transgenic lines was 14.4%, while that of the untransformed control was 14.0% (see figure).

These results showed that transgenic lines expressing one and two *Bt* genes have no adverse effects on the presence of nontarget insects belonging to the insect orders Hemiptera, Homoptera, and Orthoptera.

References

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